

Isometry test: Metric invariance under coordinate transformations

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Abstract

A simple scheme is developed to test whether a given coordinate transformation of the metric tensor is an isometry or not. The test can also be used to predict the time dilation caused by any type of motion for a given space-time metric.

Keywords and phrases: general relativity; coordinate transformation; diffeomorphism; isometry; symmetries.

1 Introduction

Isometry is any coordinate transformation which preserves the distances. In special relativity, Minkowski metric has Poincare as the group of isometries, and the corresponding coordinate transformations leave the physical properties of the metric like distance invariant. In general relativity any infinitesimal transformation along Killing vector fields is an isometry. These are infinitesimal transformations generated by one parameter ϵ

$$x'^{\mu} = x^{\mu} + \epsilon V^{\mu} \quad (1)$$

Here $V(x) = V^{\mu} \partial_{\mu}$ can be thought of like a vector field with components given as

$$V^{\mu}(x) = \frac{dx'^{\mu}}{d\epsilon}(x) \quad (2)$$

All coordinate transformations generated such can be checked for isometry by calculating Lie derivative of the metric tensors along the vector field V . If the Lie derivative vanishes then the transformation is an isometry and vector field V is called Killing Vector field [Wald (1984); Weinberg (1972)]. Killing vector fields are used to study the symmetries of the space-time metrics and the associated conserved quantities. But there are some challenges in using Killing equations for checking isometry. Coordinate transformations which are either discrete (not generated by the one-parameter ϵ) or not possible to define as integral curves of a vectors field cannot be checked for isometry using this scheme. Some examples of these type of transformations are given below.

1. Time coordinate transformation in Schwarzschild metric as given below

$$t' = at, \quad (3)$$

where a is an arbitrary constant. This can be viewed both as an active transformation in which the proper time is boosted or as a passive transformation in which it is just relabeled. As Schwarzschild metric has space-time symmetries of spatial rotations and time translation and boost along any dimension is not a symmetry, any scaling or boost/ dilation of time coordinate is doubtful to be an isometry. In fact any arbitrary scaling or boost/ dilation of time coordinate without an accompanying motion is in doubt as this leads to change of proper time for a stationary observer which is an invariant.

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- Boost along ϕ axis by a constant angular velocity a

$$\phi' = \phi + at \tag{4}$$

This represents an orbital motion with velocity given as $v = a.r \sin \theta$. As any motion should cause time dilation we expect some transformation of time coordinate to accompany this transformation but since the motion is not inertial it is not very clear should be the transformation to reflect the time dilation caused by motion, especially for metrics other than Minkowski metric.

As there is no easy way to check the isometry for these type of coordinate transformations, many people mistakenly assume that all arbitrary transformations like these preserve the metric. One can possibly use the Cartan-Karlhede algorithm to check if any two given metrics, which are a coordinate transformation of each other, are physically same. This involves comparing two sets of invariants, consisting of the curvature tensors and a finite number of it's covariant derivatives calculated using the two metrics [Karlhede (1980)]. But since the invariants are expressed in different coordinate systems, they may sometimes appear to be different despite being equivalent. Therefore this solution is not as straightforward and practical in many scenarios. Thus there is a need for a relatively easier scheme to check if a given coordinate transformation $x \rightarrow x'$ preserves the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$. That is the motivation for current work. To achieve this I will first discuss how many types of coordinate transformations are there in section 2 . Next I will develop the isometry-test In section 3 to check if a given coordinate transformation preserves a given metric or not. Section 4 checks some sample transformations for isometry using the new scheme developed here.

2 Defining the Coordinate transformations

In differential geometry there are 3 different ways coordinate transformations can happen.

- Change of coordinate system

A local coordinate chart (U, ψ) on an n dimensional manifold M is a a homeomorphism $\psi : U \rightarrow R^n$ such that each point $P(x)$ in open subset U of M is mapped to an n-tuple $x = (x^1, \dots, x^n)$ in a subset of R^n . If there exists another local coordinate chart (U', ψ') which maps each point $P'(x')$ in open subset U' of M to n-tuple $x' = (x'^1, \dots, x'^n)$ in a different subset of R^n and if $U \cup U' \neq \emptyset$ then a continuous differentiable function $x' = \gamma(x)$ having a continuous differentiable inverse function $x = \gamma'(x')$ for all overlapping open sets U and U' is a change in coordinate system. Some common examples of coordinate systems are Cartesian coordinate system and spherical coordinate system. The transformation function for change of coordinate system case is defined simply as

$$\gamma = \psi' \circ \psi^{-1} \tag{5}$$

All such coordinate transformations are isometries by default since we are just remapping the points on manifold from one subset of R^n to another. See figure 1

Figure 1: Change of coordinate system

Figure 2: Diffeomorphism which is an isometry

2. Diffeomorphism

Diffeomorphism are the transformations which do not change the coordinate system but still change the n-tuple values of all points on the manifold. For example moving the origin or rotating the coordinate axes of any coordinate system changes the 3-tuple values of all points on the manifold but the coordinate system still remains the same. These transformations are called passive or active transformations depending on how we visualize such change. We can imagine points on the manifold remaining fixed and only frame of reference being moved, treating these as passive transformations, or we can imagine frame of reference being fixed and all the points on manifold moving thus treating the transformation as active transformation. As there is no preferred frame of reference in relativity, there is no way to differentiate between the two. As transformations of this kind are a mapping of points on the manifold M to some other points on same manifold M ($\phi : M \rightarrow M$) or even to points on another manifold N which may or may not be physically same as M ($\phi : M \rightarrow N$). For example a diffeomorphism from points on a two sphere to points on another two sphere with a different radius is not an isometry as physical properties like radius and curvature for both spheres are different. The transformation function for diffeomorphism is defined as

$$\gamma = \psi \circ \phi \circ \psi^{-1} \tag{6}$$

See figures 2 and 3

3. Combination of diffeomorphism and change of coordinate system

Finally we can have transformations which are a combination of the two transformations as mentioned above. The transformation function in this case is

$$\gamma = \psi' \circ \phi \circ \psi^{-1} \tag{7}$$

It is always possible to break down this as a two step transformation.

$$\gamma = (\psi' \circ \psi^{-1}) \circ (\psi \circ \phi \circ \psi^{-1}) \tag{8}$$

See figure 4

As we can see only those transformations which involve a diffeomorphism ϕ need to be tested for isomorphism while simple coordinate system changes are isometry by default. One however needs to be careful to differentiate between the two for a given transformation function γ . It takes set of all n-tuples belonging to a subset of real numbers called domain and maps those to set of n-tuples belonging to another subset of real numbers called the co-domain. Clearly when the domain and co-domain for γ are same then it's a mapping of all points on the manifold to some other points on the same or on a different manifold, which by definition is diffeomorphism. On the other hand if domain and co-domain of the transformation function are different then it obviously involves a change of coordinate system.

Figure 3: Diffeomorphism which is not an isometry

Figure 4: Combination of diffeomorphism and change of coordinate system

For example Cartesian coordinates in 3 dimensions have 3-tuples in R^3 while Spherical coordinates in 3 dimensions have 3-tuples in $R \times A^2$ where $A = \{x|x \in R, 0 \leq x \leq 2\pi\}$. As discussed above any change in coordinate system is an isometry by default so I devise the isometry-test only for diffeomorphism in next section.

3 Isometry test for diffeomorphism

In differential geometry metric tensor provides the notion of distance hence isometry in general relativity means any transformation which preserves the metric tensor. A metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}(x)$ transforms under change of coordinates $x \rightarrow x'$ as

$$g'_{\mu\nu}(x') = \frac{\partial x^\rho}{\partial x'^\mu} \frac{\partial x^\sigma}{\partial x'^\nu} g_{\rho\sigma}(x) \quad (9)$$

Line element $ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$ at two different points on same or a different manifold P and P' with coordinates x and x' has difference in length given by

$$g_{\mu\nu}(x') dx'^\mu dx'^\nu - g_{\mu\nu}(x) dx^\mu dx^\nu \quad (10)$$

Using equation 9 we can write this as

$$(g_{\mu\nu}(x') - g'_{\mu\nu}(x')) dx'^\mu dx'^\nu \quad (11)$$

Isometry demands that line element has same length at both x and x' , which leads us to condition

$$g_{\mu\nu}(x') = g'_{\mu\nu}(x') \quad (12)$$

Above equality from passive point of view means that new metric at point P' with coordinate x' is same as the old metric at another point P with same value of the old coordinate, i.e. $x(P) = x'(P')$. From active point of view this is same as saying that metric has same form at two different points x and x' within same coordinates, i.e. for $x(P) \neq x'(P')$

$$g_{\mu\nu}(x') = g_{\mu\nu}(x) \quad (13)$$

Using equations 12, 13 and 9 we get

$$g_{\mu\nu}(x) = \frac{\partial x^\rho}{\partial x'^\mu} \frac{\partial x^\sigma}{\partial x'^\nu} g_{\rho\sigma}(x) \quad (14)$$

The equation above is nothing but set of conditions on the coordinate transformation of type diffeomorphism $x \rightarrow x'$ for the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ to be form invariant and thus can be used as isometry test for a coordinate transformation on a given metric. At first sight the condition seems rather restrictive and not very useful but as we will see in next section, it has not only the ability to check if any diffeomorphism is an isometry, but also has the power to make some predictions as well.

4 Examples of the isometry test

Before we can use this as isometry test for some interesting cases, I will show that it works for Poincare group which is the isometry group for Minkowski space-time metric and has translations along the four dimensions, and rotation and boost along the spatial axes.

1. Translations

Translations are defined as $t' = t+a, x' = x+b, y' = y+c, z' = z+d$ for arbitrary constants a, b, c, d . This means that $\frac{dx^\mu}{dx'^\nu} = \delta_\nu^\mu$. The transformed metric is thus unchanged and since $\frac{dx^\mu}{dx'^\nu} = \delta_\nu^\mu$ the equation 14 also holds good.

2. Rotations

Rotation by an angle θ in 3 dimensions around axis $\mu = x, y, z$ is given by matrix equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = R_\mu \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Where rotation matrices R_μ are defined as

$$R_x = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

$$R_y = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & \sin \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

$$R_z = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Multiplying equation 15 with inverse rotation matrices R_μ^{-1} gives transformation relation $x' \rightarrow x$

$$R_\mu^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = R_\mu^{-1} R_\mu \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Inverse rotation matrices R_μ^{-1} are calculated as

$$R_x^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ 0 & -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

$$R_y^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (21)$$

$$R_z^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (22)$$

Using above we can easily prove the equation 14 for $\mu\nu = xx, yy, zz$

3. Boost

Boost along the spatial axes x, y and z are defined as $x' = x + at, y' = y + bt, z' = z + ct$ for arbitrary constants a, b, c, d . Equation 14 is easily shown to be satisfied for $\mu\nu = xx, yy$ and zz . For $\mu\nu = tt$ equation 14 is calculated as

$$g_{tt} = -\left(\frac{dt'}{dt}\right)^2 (c^2 - (a^2 + b^2 + c^2)) = -c^2 \left(\frac{dt'}{dt}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \quad (23)$$

Here $v = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2}$ is the velocity. Solving this gives

$$t' = t \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (24)$$

Which is the expected time dilation as per special relativity. Thus the isometry test proposed in this paper has the power to make prediction for time dilation caused by motion. This increases the utility of the isometry test to beyond just a simple test for coordinate transformations. As we will see later it can be used to predict this for any kind of motion in any given space-time.

Having shown that the isometry test works for simplest isometry group we now test the same for two transformation equations given in the beginning of this paper

1. Time coordinate boost in Schwarzschild metric

$$t' = at \quad (25)$$

Using this RHS of equation 14 for $\mu\nu = tt$ is calculated as

$$-\frac{c^2}{a^2} \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2}\right) \neq g_{tt} \quad (26)$$

Thus boost or scaling of time coordinate in Schwarzschild metric is not isometric as we expected it to be.

2. Boost along ϕ axis by a constant angular velocity $a = v/r \sin \theta$

$$\phi' = \phi + at \quad (27)$$

Where v is the orbital velocity along a constant angle θ . We can test this transformation for any metric, including the Schwarzschild metric. It's easy to show that equation 14 is satisfied for $\mu\nu = rr, \theta\theta$ and $\phi\phi$. For $\mu\nu = tt$ equation 14 is calculated as

$$-c^2 \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) = -c^2 \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) \left(\frac{dt}{dt'}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2 \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)}\right) \quad (28)$$

Solving above gives

$$t' = t \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2 \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)}} \quad (29)$$

This result reduces to Lorentz time dilation in absence of any mass but deviates slightly in Schwarzschild metric. We have used here the isometry test to predict the time dilation caused by an orbital motion in a space-time which is not Minkowskian¹. This highlights the utility of this work as much more than just a simple isometry test for coordinate transformations.

5 Conclusion

Coordinate transformations are a source of confusion in general relativity as it is not easy to figure out which transformations preserve the metric and which one do not, except for the infinitesimal transformations along the Killing vector fields generated by the one parameter ϵ . This work provides a way out of this confusion and allows one to check if any arbitrary coordinate transformation is isometry or not. The process involves first categorizing the transformation as a change in coordinate system, a diffeomorphism or a combination of the two. Using equation 14 one can easily confirm if the coordinate transformations of type diffeomorphism preserve the form of the metric and are thus isometry or not. In addition to that it also helps to predict the time dilation expected due to any kind of motion in any space-time metric.

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¹This however remains to be confirmed experimentally